

LTD data dictionary

From the PDF to an SQLite file

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Introduction

The “Legacy Data Dictionary.pdf” file provides metadata that are essential to understand the data tables provided by Radtke et al. (2023).

The document has 89 pages, access to the information is cumbersome and inefficient. To enhance accessibility, the main contents have been transferred into an SQLite file, containing the description of the ‘LEGACY data tables columns’ and the corresponding ‘detailed explanations’. The SQLIT version of the Legacy Data Dictionary can be downloaded here: https://gitlab.com/NuoroForestrySchool/data-scraping-from-pdf-to-sqlite/-/raw/main/LegacyTreeData_DataDictionary.sqlite

REFERENCES

Radtke, P.; Walker, D.; Frank, J.; Weiskittel, A.; MacFarlane, D. [et al.]. 2023. LegacyTreeData [Dataset]. Version 2. Blacksburg, VA: Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University, University Libraries. <https://doi.org/10.7294/22582432>

```
library(tidyverse)
library(pdftools)

local_copy <- fs::path("DATA", "Legacy Data Dictionary.pdf")
if (!file.exists(local_copy))
  download.file("https://data.lib.vt.edu/ndownloader/files/40083559",
               local_copy)

raw_data <- pdf_data(local_copy)
```

```

raw_data2 <- map_df(1:length(raw_data),
                  \ (p) add_column(raw_data[[p]], page = p, .before = 1)) |>
  arrange(page, y, x)
rm(raw_data)

```

Scraping 'columns descriptions'

```

# For each table,
TabLimits <- raw_data2 |>
  mutate(r2 = lag(y, 2)) |>
  # the 'name' is the first word of the lines
  # containing \\/
  filter(text == "Detailed") |>
  select(page, r2) |>
  inner_join(raw_data2, by = join_by(page, r2 == y)) |>
  filter(x == 31) |>
  select(Table = text) |>
  # column descriptions
  bind_cols(
    # start on the lines with '1' on the left
    raw_data2 |>
      inner_join(raw_data2 |>
                filter(text == '1',
                       between(x, 41, 57)) |>
                select(page, y),
                by = join_by(page, y)) |>
    # and \\/ at the end
    filter(text == 'VARCHAR2', x == 504) |>
    select(p1 = page, r1 = y)
  ) |>
  bind_cols(# while they on 3 lines before the one
    raw_data2 |>
      mutate(r2 = lag(y, 3)) |>
      # containing \\/
      filter(text == "Detailed") |>
      select(p2 = page, r2))

getTab <- function(p1, r1, p2, r2, raw) {
  # p1=69; p2=69; r1=283; r2=511; raw=raw_data2

  TabLines <- raw |>
  dplyr::filter((page == p1 & y >= r1) | page > p1) |>

```

```

dplyr::filter((page == p2 & y <= r2) | page < p2)

Caption0 <- TabLines |>
  filter(between(x, 186, 503)) |>
  nest(.by = c(page, y)) |>
  mutate(t2 = map_chr(data, \(d) paste(d$text, collapse = " "))) |>
  select(-data)
aCapo <- TabLines |>
  summarise(xmin = min(x), .by = c(page, y)) |>
  mutate(aCapo = xmin == 186) |>
  arrange(page, y) |>
  mutate(yb = lag(y)) |>
  filter(aCapo) |>
  select(page, y, yb)
Caption <- Caption0 |>
  anti_join(aCapo, by = join_by(page, y)) |>
  left_join(Caption0 |>
    inner_join(aCapo, by = join_by(page, y)),
    by = join_by(page, y == yb)) |>
  # filter(!is.na(t2.y)) |>
  mutate(t2 = paste(t2.x,
    map_chr(t2.y, \(x) if_else(is.na(
      x
    ), "", x))))

getCol <- function(tab, x1, x2 = x1) {
  tab |>
    filter(between(x, x1, x2)) |>
    select(text) |>
    pluck(1)
}

tibble(
  No = getCol(TabLines, 41, 57),
  ColName = getCol(TabLines, 70),
  DataType = getCol(TabLines, 504),
  Caption = Caption$t2
)
}

getTab2 <- function(Table, p1, r1, p2, r2) {
  getTab(p1, r1, p2, r2, raw_data2) |>
  add_column(.before = 1, Table = Table)
}

```

```
Dict <- TabLimits |>
  pmap_df(getTab2)
```

Scraping 'detailed explanations'

```
# 'detailed explanations' end
#   the line before           'Appendix'   \\/
end <- raw_data2 |> filter(page == 87, text == "I.")

# sections limits for each table
DetailedExplim <- raw_data2 |>
  # start after the line with \\/
  filter(text == 'Detailed') |>
  select(page, y) |>
  inner_join(raw_data2, by = join_by(page, y)) |>
  filter(x == 31) |>
  select(Table = text, p1 = page, r1 = y) |>
  # and end before successive 'LEGACY'
  bind_cols(
    raw_data2 |>
      filter(text == 'LEGACY', x == 61) |>
      select(page, y) |>
      inner_join(raw_data2, by = join_by(page, y)) |>
      filter(x == 102) |>
      select(p2 = page, r2 = y, TABLE = text)
  ) |>
  mutate(p2 = lead(p2), r2 = lead(r2)) |>
  # except for the last, that ends before Appendix 'I.'
  mutate(p2 = ifelse(is.na(p2), end$page, p2)) |>
  mutate(r2 = ifelse(is.na(r2), end$y, r2))

getExp_s <- function(Table, p1, r1, p2, r2) {

  DELines <- raw_data2 |>
    filter((page == p1 & y > r1) | page > p1) |>
    filter((page == p2 & y < r2) | page < p2) |>
    arrange(page, y, x) |>
    mutate(No = if_else(x == 41, text, NA)) |>
    fill(No) |>
    nest(.by = No)

  map_df(DELines$data,
```

```

      \(ElLines)
      tibble(
        No = ElLines$text[1],
        ColName = ElLines$text[2],
        Explan = paste(ElLines$text[3:nrow(ElLines)], collapse = " ")
      ) |>
      add_column(Table = Table, .before = 1)
    }

    DetExpl_s <- DetailedExpLim |>
      select(-TABLE) |>
      pmap_df(getExp_s)

```

Conclusion

```

if(!identical(Dict$ColName, DetExpl_s$ColName)){
  cat(" *** WARNING *** ColNames should be all the same in the two sets",
      "and are not!")
}

library(DBI)
dbfn <- "LegacyTreeData_DataDictionary.sqlite"
conn <- dbConnect(RSQLite::SQLite(), dbfn)
dbWriteTable(conn, "DataDictionary", Dict, overwrite = T)
dbWriteTable(conn, "DetailesExplanations", DetExpl_s, overwrite = T)
dbDisconnect(conn)

cat("The tables have respectively\n",
    "DataDictionary ", nrow(Dict), "rows", "\n",
    "DetailedExplanations", nrow(DetExpl_s), "rows"
    )

```

The tables have respectively
 DataDictionary 706 rows
 DetailedExplanations 706 rows